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Foreign Private Investment And Growth Of Nigerian Economy

¹Oguocha, L. Ukamaka & ²Onuora K. Joshua

^{1&2}Department of Accountancy,
Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University, Igbariam, Nigeria

ABSTRACT

This study investigated the foreign private investment and growth of Nigerian economy for the period of 1990-2023. The specific objectives were to: Determine the effect of real investment on growth of Nigerian economy. Analyze the effect of portfolio investment on growth of Nigerian economy. Ordinary Least Square (OLS) method of data analysis was adopted because of its Best Linear Unbiased Estimators (BLUE) properties. The data for the variables used were sourced from the Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletin. The variables used were real investment and portfolio investment as independent variables, while real gross domestic product was used as dependent variable. The study adopted the descriptive statistics approach, as well as Error Correction Mechanism to analyses the corrected data. E-View software was used for the analysis. The study found that, real investment has significant effect on growth of Nigerian economy. Portfolio investment has significant effect on growth of Nigerian economy. It was conclude that the foreign private investment has significant and positive effect on real gross domestic product in Nigeria. The study recommends that; Efforts should be made to channel foreign investment into non-oil sectors such as agriculture, manufacturing, ICT, solid minerals, and renewable energy. This will create jobs, enhance industrialization, and promote sustainable growth. Institutions such as the Nigerian Investment Promotion Commission (NIPC) should be further empowered to facilitate and monitor investments.

Keywords: Real investment, Portfolio investment, real gross domestic product, foreign private investment

1.1 INTRODUCTION

Private investment (PI) is key to the economic prosperity of every nation, and this has been demonstrated by emerging and newly industrialized nations. Foreign private investment (FPI) has remained a major driver of economic growth and development across the globe. In developing economies like Nigeria, FPI plays a significant role in bridging the savings investment gap, generating employment, stimulating technological transfer, and enhancing access to international markets (Nwangwu, Ohanyere, Nwangwu, & Atueyi, 2025). According to the classical and neoclassical growth theories, capital accumulation is a critical determinant of long-run economic growth, and since most developing countries often face inadequate domestic savings, FPI serves as an alternative source of finance for development (Todaro & Smith, 2015).

It is the role of the foreign private investment to augment domestic resources to enable them to be more efficient in their development programmes and as such raise the standard of living of the citizens. FDI has been seen over some periods of time as a means of boosting the economy as it helps to transfer technological and managerial practices through the host countries and thereby exhibiting more positive

external influences on the economy (Sadiq et al., 2021, Ohanyere Arinze, & Atueyi 2025). Nigeria, as the largest economy in Africa, has over the decades attracted considerable foreign private investment, particularly in the oil and gas, telecommunications, banking, and manufacturing sectors. The liberalization of the economy in the 1980s under the Structural Adjustment Programme (SAP), coupled with economic reforms in the 2000s, further opened up the Nigerian economy to foreign investors. Despite these efforts, the level of FPI inflow has remained volatile due to political instability, weak infrastructure, policy inconsistencies, insecurity, and corruption (Ifechukwu-jacobs, & Atueyi, 2024).

The relationship between FPI and economic growth in Nigeria has been a subject of debate among scholars and policymakers. While some argue that FPI enhances growth through capital inflow, job creation, and improved productivity, others maintain that the benefits are limited due to profit repatriation, dominance of the oil sector, and the crowding out of local enterprises (Adeleke, Olowe & Fasesin, 2014, Ifechukwu-Jacobs, Arinze, & Nwangwu, & Atueyi, 2025). Thus, examining the effect of FPI on Nigeria's economic growth is not only relevant but also timely, especially given the country's current quest for economic diversification and sustainable development. The issue of foreign private and foreign direct investment and economic growth has been a topic of interest and discussion among scholars and researchers. In the late 1970s and early 1980s, most developing countries of Africa including Nigeria experienced unprecedented and severe economic crises. These crises manifested it in several ways such as persistent macroeconomic imbalances, widening savings-investment gap, high rates of domestic inflation, chronic balance of payment problems and huge budget deficits. (Onya, Arinze, & Atueyi, 2025). Greene and Villannueve (1991) attributed the problem to the decline in investment rates in the affected economies. The misalignment between savings and capital requirements of most economies of the world especially some developing and sub Saharan Africa (Nigeria) has been seen as a major reason why they cannot attend their desired growth level. This is also, seen as a result of insufficient domestic private investment to boost and enable those countries achieve their target.

Despite Nigeria's enormous natural resources and large market size, the country has not fully harnessed the potential benefits of foreign private investment. Although FPI inflows have increased intermittently, their contribution to sustainable growth remains questionable. For instance, a significant portion of FPI is concentrated in the oil and gas sector, with little spillover effects on other sectors of the economy. This sectoral concentration reduces the extent to which FPI can stimulate broad-based growth. Moreover, challenges such as inadequate infrastructure, insecurity (including insurgency and banditry), corruption, foreign exchange instability, and weak institutional frameworks have discouraged long-term foreign investors. As a result, Nigeria has experienced fluctuating growth rates despite high volumes of capital inflows in certain years. The problem this study seeks to address, therefore, is the paradox of rising foreign private investment and

1.2 Objectives of the Study

The broad objective of the study is to examine foreign private investment and growth of Nigerian economy. The following are the specific objectives:

- i. Determine the effect of real investment on growth of Nigerian economy.
- ii. Analyze the effect of portfolio investment on growth of Nigerian economy.

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Conceptual Review

2.1.1 Concept of Foreign Private Investment (FPI)

Foreign Private Investment (FPI) refers to private capital flows into a country, comprising Foreign Direct Investment (FDI), which involves acquiring a controlling stake in a business and operating physical assets, and Foreign Portfolio Investment (FPI), which involves investing in financial assets like shares and bonds without gaining operational control. FPI provides crucial finance for developing economies, stimulating growth through technological transfer, increased productivity, job creation, and tax revenue, though FDI is generally considered more beneficial due to its greater potential for positive externalities and stability.

According to Ariyo (1988), Foreign Private Investment can be classified as Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) and Foreign Portfolio Investment (PFI). FDI is an investment in real assets where real assets consist of physical things such as factories, land, capital goods, infrastructure and inventories. The Multinational Corporations (MNCs) is chief source of DFI. This may come in both joint ventures as well as fully owned subsidiaries. Whereas, international investment in financial assets such as shares, debentures and bonds are called PFI (Foreign Portfolio Investment). Foreign Private Investment is a significant component of foreign private capital flows that provide much needed finance to increase the use of existing capacity to stimulate new investment in developing countries. FPI has two major components: portfolio investment and direct investment. Portfolio investment is the form of equity capital either thus empowers its owner to flow dividends. On the other hand, foreign direct investment enables the foreigner to own the physical productive assets, which operates. Large multinational or transnational corporations essentially carry out this flow of resources with headquarters in the developed nations. Flow of financial capital is by private international banks (Ekpo, 1997).

According to Obadan (2004) foreign private capital flows do not constitute economic aid, as they do not provide resources to developing countries on concessionary terms even though they may yield substantial benefits. They are flows that originate in the private sectors of the donor/lending country and are almost always motivated by normal commercial considerations of profit maximization. Foreign portfolio investment consists of the acquisition of assets by a foreign national or company in a domestic stock/market. In order words, it refers to the holding of transferable securities(issued or guaranteed by the government of the importing country), equity shares; debentures, bonds, promissory notes and money market instruments issued in a domestic market by the nationals of some other countries (Odozi 1995).

Foreign Private Sector Real Investment

Foreign private sector real investment refers to the inflow of capital from private entities (such as multinational corporations, institutional investors, or individuals) into the tangible and productive sectors of a host economy. Unlike portfolio investments, which are short-term and speculative in nature, real investment involves long-term commitments such as the establishment of factories, acquisition of machinery, construction of infrastructure, or direct participation in productive ventures. It is often equated with foreign direct investment (FDI) when the investment translates into significant ownership and control in a host-country enterprise.

According to the United Nations Conference on Trade and Development (UNCTAD, 2023), real investment by foreign private actors is an important driver of development because it supplements domestic savings, enhances capital formation, and creates employment. In Nelson (2016), this is conceptualized as an investment which involves the injection of foreign capital by foreign investors into a company that domiciles and operates in a country or nation other than that of the investors. Foreign private sector real investment is also referred to as foreign direct investment which involves the transfer of the complete productive and organizational complex, embracing a set of factors of production such as capital, technology, knowledge, and marketing and management skills. It may also be referred to as a direct investment into production in a country other than that of the investor's origin, which could be in the form of acquisition of an existing company in a foreign country or by expansion of operations of the existing business in the foreign country.

Sodersten (2004) opine that foreign real investment occurs when there is a transmission of a perceptible and imperceptible asset from a business entity which has bulk of its shares directly and indirectly in the custody of another business entity of foreign nationality into the host country with full or fractional control of the owner of the assets. That it is normally done with the intention of creating wealth in the host country.

Foreign Private Sector Portfolio Investment

Foreign Private Portfolio Investment (FPPI) refers to the purchase of financial assets such as stocks, bonds, treasury bills, and other money market instruments in a country's capital market by non-resident private investors. Unlike Foreign Direct Investment (FDI), which involves long-term commitment and

control in production or business activities, FPPI is essentially short-term, market-driven, and primarily motivated by financial returns and risk diversification (IMF, 2009).

This entails an investment in money market instruments comprising treasury bills, treasure certificates, government bonds to mention but a few, and the investors are predominantly foreign investors whose countries of origin are other than that of the domestic economy. Portfolio investment is also referred to as indirect or rentier investment. In the portfolio investment, ownership and use of capital remain separated from each other. A foreign portfolio investor has only a de jure control over the invested capital without being a de-facto or having an effective control over the management, policies and other decision-making processes of the firm in which investment has been made.

2.2 Theoretical Framework

2.2.1. The Neo-classical Growth Model

The Solow and Swan (1956) models of economic growth, which commonly represent the Neoclassical model are based on an aggregate production function (Cobb-Douglas) and a capital accumulation equation. These models do not account for technological progress and predict that the level of per capita income is determined by the population growth rate and the investment rate. Accordingly, economic growth can happen only temporarily and lasts only until income per capita reached its steady state level. The second model introduced by Solow in 1956 incorporates technology as exogenous variable. The important implication of the neoclassical growth model is the level of per capita output is determined by the level of technology, investment rate and population growth rate. While sustained growth rate of per capita output overtime is determined by technological changes.

Other temporary shocks such as policy changes can affect growth only temporarily just until a new steady state level is reached. Hence, according to Solow's model, per capita output defers across countries and overtime is explained by the country's population growth, investment rate and technology (Jones 1995, Romer 1986). In this model, if there is no technological progress, steady state per capita output does not grow and it depends on exogenous factors (that is technological progress and population growth). In this framework, in the short run, an increase in the savings rate increase per capita income. However, due to diminishing returns to capital, per capita output in the long run grows at the rate of exogenously given technological progress. Although economic policies can affect the level of output (growth rate) when the economy is in transition from one steady state to another, they do not affect steady state economic growth. One might object to the neoclassical model on the grounds that it does not, in the end, shed light on economic growth. In the steady state of the neo-classical model, all growth is due to improvement in technology, but model unravels the mystery of economic growth simply by assuming that there is economic growth (Mankiw 1995). In other words, the neoclassical growth model is criticized on the grounds that it leaves technological growth as an exogenous factor and without technological growth, the model asserts that economic growth will, ultimately, cease.

2.3 Empirical Review

Ugbaka and Ojikpong, (2024) examined empirically, whether or not foreign private investment (FDI), bank credit to the private sector (BCR), manufactured goods import (MGM), real per capita income (PCY) and inflation rate (INF) impact significantly and positively on manufacturing output (MNQ) in Nigeria over the sample period of twenty-seven year from 1995 and 2022. The newly developed bounds testing approach to co-integration was adopted in the study. The results obtained reveal that both the short-run and long-run growth effects of manufacturing output in Nigeria are significant and positive. These findings on foreign private investment underscores the imperative for adopting appropriate measures that would attract more foreign investments to the manufacturing sector in Nigeria. Having ascertained the significance of foreign private investment positively influencing manufacturing output in Nigeria, the study submits that a set of policies to the Nigerian government with a view to enhancing foreign private investment and fostering manufacturing sector's growth in Nigeria should be vigorously pursued.

Ekpo, Iwatt and Uduimoh, (2023) examined the impact of private investment on economic performance in Nigeria using time series data from 1980 -2018. Multiple regression and co-integration methods are employed to analyze the data. The objectives of this study is to, among other things, examine the casual relationship between private investment and economic growth in Nigeria and to investigate the impact of private domestic investment on economic performance in Nigeria. Being a time series data, the first step is to test for the stationarity of the data by using Phillips Perron-Fuller unit root test. Ordinary least square (OLS) and Auto regressive distributed lag (ARDL) technique is used to estimate the models. The findings from the analysis using the Ordinary Least Square (OLS) and Auto Regressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) methods show the following: that there is no causal relationship between private investment and economic performance in Nigeria. Private Domestic Investment (PDI) recorded a positive but insignificant impact on economic performance (RGDPR) both in the short run and long run; unemployment rate reveal a negative but insignificant impact on economic performance (RGDPR) in the short run but the impact is statistically significant in the long run. There is no long run significant impact of Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) on economic performance in Nigeria, Trade Openness showed a significant inverse relationship with Misery Rate which was proxy for economic performance. The co-integration tests also confirm the existence of long run relationship between the variables and results gotten from stationarity and normality test reveal that the model is fairly well specified and could be used for policy analysis.

Edem, et al. (2024) examined the impact of foreign private sector investment on Nigerian economy. The study specifically explored the impacts of foreign private sector real investment (FPSRI) and foreign private sector portfolio investment (FPSPI) on the Real Gross Domestic Product (RGDP) of the Real Gross Domestic Product (RGDP) of Nigeria. The data for the study were sourced and obtained from the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) Statistical Bulletin and World Bank Database from 1981 to 2020. Econometric techniques of unit root, integration, ARDL regression, error correction model were employed in analyzing the data. The results showed that foreign private sector real investment (FPSRI) exerted significant positive impact on real gross domestic product (RGDP) growth during the period studied where as foreign private sector portfolio investment (FPSPI) exerted significant negative impact on RGDP growth both short and long runs.

Salisu, et al. (2018) determined and explored the economic impact of foreign private investment on the economic growth and development of Nigeria over the period under study which is between 1980 and 2015. Unit root test was conducted based on ADF and PP technique, and all the variables were found to be stationary at level. Johansen co integration test was also employed to check the long run relationship among the variables of study, the result reveal the existence of long run equilibrium. Short run relation was also examined using ECM technique, result confirm a short run relation among the variables. OLS method was employed to estimate the parameters of the model. Empirical result from revealed that, Foreign Private Investment (FPI) has a negative and significant effect on capital formation in Nigeria.

Ofosu-Mensah Ababio, et al. (2022) surveyed and synthesized the literature on foreign and domestic private investment over the period 1980–2022 with evidence from developing and emerging economies. The documentary sources method was used to examine one hundred and forty (140) peer-reviewed articles (selected based on source, journal of publication, database, time frame, relevance language, geographical restrictions, and search descriptions) published in a broad range of internationally recognized journals, with special analytical focus placed on forty (40) recent articles. It provides fresh evidence that literature on overall private investment and that of foreign direct investment have been given paramount interest and attention, but domestic private investment has received relatively diminutive attention to date. This review will serve as a roadmap, indicating the current state, contributions made, and unsolved issues in the extant studies as well as situating works to enrich the literature. It, therefore, offers specific directions for researchers, academics, and practitioners.

METHODS

3.1 Research Design

In the course of this study, *ex-post facto* to design was adopted. According to Devin, *ex-post facto* to research design is a quasi experimental study examining how an independent variable, present prior to the study affects a dependent variable. Ex-post facto research design was used in the course of this study because the collected data used in this study cannot be controlled or manipulated.

3.2 Model Specification

The specification of econometrics model is always based on econometrics theory or any available information relating to the phenomenon being studied (koustsoyiannis 1997), hence the specification of the model adopted for this investigation is implicitly stated as follows

$$RGDP = F (RIV, PFI).$$

Where

RGDP	-	Real gross domestic product
RIV	-	Real investment
PFI	-	Portfolio investment
F	-	Functional notation

The above equation can be put in an econometric form as;

$$RGDP = b_0 + b_1 RIV + b_2 PFI + U$$

Where

B0	=	Autonomous or intercept
B1	=	Coefficient of parameter RIV
B2	=	Coefficient of parameter PFI
U	=	Stochastic variable or error term

Our model can be also be stated in a logged form as

$$\text{LogRGDP} = C + B_1 \text{LogRIV} + \text{LOG} B_2 \text{PFI} + \mu$$

3.3 Methods of Evaluation

Estimates and evaluation of the model is purely a technical stage which requires knowledge of various econometric method, their implications and economic meanings for the estimates of the parameters. For this purpose and in Oder to enhance the robustness of the empirical analysis, the result of the regression will be classified under three groups namely;

- 1) Economic a’p priori criteria
- 2) Statistical criteria (first-order test)
- 3) Econometrics criteria (second-order test)

a) Economics a’p priori criteria

Theoretical a’p priori evaluation of the sign of the parameter will be employed as determinant by economic theory. This will be by evaluating to see if the coefficients conform to standard economic theory expectation

Therefore, it is theoretically expected that fiscal policy measures should have positive relationship with foreign private investment, furthermore, it is expected that foreign private investment should have negative sign with the real gross domestic product

b) Statistical criteria (first-order test)

c) These are determine by the statistical reliability of the estimates of the parameters the most widely used statistical criteria are

i) Test of goodness of fit (R^2)

The coefficient of determination R^2 shows how good the fit of the regression line is put differently, how well the regression fits the data. this is important because the closer the observation to the regression line, the better is the explanation to the variation of Y by the explanatory variables under study, the adjusted R^2 will be analyses to account for the loss in the degree of freedom and total variation on the dependent variables explained by the model

ii) T-test

The result of the t-test would be used to judge where the variables are significant or not, it tests the individual statistical significance of the model.

iii) F-test

This test will be used to assess the significance of the overall regression model

(c) Econometrics Criteria (Second-Order Test)

These are set by econometrics theory and aims at the investigation of whether the assumption of the econometrics method employed are satisfied or not. In order words they determine the reliability of the statistical criteria and established weather the estimates has the desired properties of unbiasedness, consistency.etc

i) Autocorrelation test

To test the presence of autocorrelation in the model and also validity of non-autocorrelation distribution assumption, the Durbin Watson test will be employed

ii) Multicollinearity test

It is to be conducted on the variables so as to measure the level of correlation between them in order to ascertain of multicollnearity or not

iii) Co-integration test

This test is carried out in order to determine the long-run relationship between the dependent and independent variables. Essentially, it is used to check if the independent variables can predict the dependent variables in the future.

iv) Unit-root test

It has been established in the literatures that most times services variables are not stationary and using non-stationary variables in the model might lead to spurious regression which cannot be used for prediction, the decision rule is thus, a variables is stationary if the absolute ADF value is higher than any of the absolute Mackinnon values.

3.4 Nature and Sources of Data

The study utilizes annual secondary time series data spanning from 1981 to 2023. The choice of data period coverage is based on availability of data. With a total of 43 observations, the estimation will have adequate degree of freedom (df) that improves statistical inferences. Thus, estimates based on this data coverage not only ensure consistency of results but also guarantee robustness of results to different diagnostics tests. These secondary sources of data for this study were sought through several editions of CBN statistical bulletin.

s/n	Variables	Sources
1	Real gross domestic product (MSO):	CBN statistical bulletin
2	Real investment	CBN statistical bulletin
3	Portfolio investment	CBN statistical bulletin

PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS OF DATA

This chapter presents the empirical results and discussion of findings, ordinary least square was used as techniques for the analysis, the result was subject to different statistical and econometrics test. We begin by discussing the order of integration of the interest variables.

4.1 Descriptive Statistics Analysis

Table 1 which displays the number of observations, mean, standard deviation, minimum and maximum values of the explained variable, and each of the explanatory variables, provides the descriptive statistics for all the variables in the model. The descriptive data of the chosen service sector that comprise our sample are displayed in the table below.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics

	LRGDP	LRIV	LPOFI
Mean	8.531691	3.066330	6.609747
Median	8.707881	2.206835	6.639819
Maximum	11.40391	8.080361	12.56804
Minimum	5.043296	-0.916291	3.183456
Std. Dev.	2.244707	2.600467	2.005052
Skewness	-0.220008	0.378370	0.578435
Kurtosis	1.624791	1.770148	3.824041
Jarque-Bera Probability	3.127222 0.209379	3.127788 0.209319	3.026087 0.220239
Sum	307.1409	110.3879	237.9509
Sum Sq. Dev.	176.3549	236.6850	140.7082
Observations	36	36	36

Source: Authors Computation, 2025

The table above indicates that the mean of Real Gross Domestic Product (RGDP) is 8.53% with standard deviation of 2.24% the minimum and maximum values of 11.4% and 5.0% respectively. The mean value of Digital tax (DT) is 4.8% with standard deviation of 1.5% the minimum and maximum values of 1.6% and 6.5% respectively. The mean value of Real investment (RIV) is 3.6% with standard deviation of 2.6%, the minimum and maximum values of -0% and 11.4% respectively. Portfolio investment mean value is 6.6% with standard deviation of 2.6%, the minimum and maximum values of 3.1% and 12.5% respectively.

These results suggest that the data are not widely dispersed from the mean because the standard deviations of all the variables are less than the mean values. Also, the skewness value of all the variables are not close to zero, it means that the distribution of the variables is symmetric in nature,. The Kurtosis values of all the variables is also closer to 3, it indicates that the shape is a normal distribution,. The P-value of Jarque-Bera test of all the variables is more than 5%, except digital vat, However, Shao (2003) submits that normality of data does not in any way affect the inferential statistics estimate to the BLUE properties. (Best, Linear, Unbiased, Estimate)

4.2 Unit Root Test

The first stage of co-integration and error correction model is to test for unit root, the whole analysis then proceed from it. There exists unit root in most macroeconomics time series. Therefore, it is necessary to analyze whether the series are stationary or not whenever time series data are involved. The presence of unit root implies that the time series under investigation is non-stationary, the absence of a unit roots shows that stochastic process is stationary. The augmented dickey-fuller (ADF) test would be employed in this test

Tables 2 Unit Root Result

Variable	ADF	Integration	Significance
RGDP	-8.137054	I (2)	1%
RIV	-5.109589	I (1)	1%
POFI	-4.594536	I (1)	1%

Source: Source: Authors Computation, 2025

Following the result of ADF test above it is observed that none of the variables are stationary at level, but the entire variables become stationary at 1st difference, except real gross domestic product who became stationary at 2nd differences. This also follows the simple rule of thumb that once a unit root is conforms, co-integration is necessary to established.

4.3 Co-integration Analysis

The aim of co-integration analysis is to determine the long-run equilibrium relationship between the variables. In the Engle-granger co integration analysis, variables of consideration are said to be co integrated or have a long-run equilibrium relationship if in the OLS regression of one variable on the others. Co-integration exists among the variables if they are integrated of the same order. The implication of this analysis is that deviation or drift may occur between the variables but this is temporary as equilibrium hold in the long run for them. In this study we used the Johansen co-integration approach to examine the existence of long-run relationship between the variables of interest. Below is the summary of co integration result

Table 3 co-integration result test

Date: 09/24/25 Time: 06:47
 Sample (adjusted): 1991 2023
 Included observations: 33 after adjustments
 Trend assumption: Linear deterministic trend
 Series: LRGDP LPFI LPOFI
 Lags interval (in first differences): 1 to 2

Unrestricted Cointegration Rank Test (Trace)

Hypothesized No. of CE(s)	Eigenvalue	Trace Statistic	0.05 Critical Value	Prob.**
None *	0.513098	29.94264	29.79707	0.0481
At most 1	0.137723	6.192777	15.49471	0.6727
At most 2	0.038712	1.302890	3.841466	0.2537

Trace test indicates 1 cointegrating eqn(s) at the 0.05 level

* denotes rejection of the hypothesis at the 0.05 level

**MacKinnon-Haug-Michelis (1999) p-values

Unrestricted Cointegration Rank Test (Maximum Eigenvalue)

Hypothesized No. of CE(s)	Eigenvalue	Max-Eigen Statistic	0.05 Critical Value	Prob.**
None *	0.513098	23.74986	21.13162	0.0209
At most 1	0.137723	4.889886	14.26460	0.7557
At most 2	0.038712	1.302890	3.841466	0.2537

Max-Eigen value test indicates 1 co-integrating equations at the 0.5 level* denotes rejection of the hypothesis at the 0.05 level **mackinnon-Haug-michelis (1999) P-values.

Trace test value and Max-Eigen indicates 1 co-integrating equations at the 0.05 level. This suggests a long run equilibrium relationship among the variables.

Co-integration is a pre-requisite for error correction mechanism following the result of co-integration, there is a long-run equilibrium relationship among the variable, hence, we can move over to error correction mechanism.

4.5 Presentation of Regression Result

Table 5 Error Correction Model Result

Dependent Variable: LRGDP
 Method: Least Squares
 Date: 09/24/25 Time: 06:48
 Sample (adjusted): 1989 2023
 Included observations: 35 after adjustments

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	0.434685	0.491542	9.021982	0.0000
LRIV	0.435440	0.076487	5.692977	0.0000
LPOFI	0.410642	0.100645	4.080118	0.0003
ECM(-1)	-0.904096	0.159237	-5.677694	0.0000
R-squared	0.728706	Mean dependent var		8.631359
Adjusted R-squared	0.732775	S.D. dependent var		2.195170
S.E. of regression	0.569161	Akaike info criterion		1.817904
Sum squared resid	10.04228	Schwarz criterion		1.995658
Log likelihood	-27.81332	Hannan-Quinn criter.		1.879265
F-statistic	158.2535	Durbin-Watson stat		1.589179
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			

Source: Source: Authors Computation, 2025

The results presented above will be analyzed using two criteria; Accounting a priori criteria, and statistical criteria

A. Accounting a priori Criteria

The a’p priori expectation is used to determine the existing Accounting theories and this indicates the signs and magnitude of our variables.

1. A regression line intercept of 0.434685 is displayed in the result in table 5. With a p-value of 0.0000, which is less than 0.05, the t-test result is 9.021982, which is positive and statistically significant. This suggests that when there is no change in the explanatory variables, the real gross domestic product will remain constant at 72% per cent annually.
2. Table 5’s regression result demonstrates a statistically significant positive correlation between real gross domestic product and real investment. Real investment has a value of 0.435440, which suggests that a 43% increase in real gross domestic product will, ceteris paribus, result in a 43% improvement in real gross domestic product. This is in line with the apriori prediction. This finding bolsters the theory that raising Real investment will improve real gross domestic product in Nigeria
3. There is a positive relationship between real gross domestic product and portfolio investment. The portfolio investment value is 0.410642. This suggests that a percent increase in the real gross domestic product will, ceteris paribus, result in a rise in real gross domestic product value of roughly by 41 percent. This is in line with the apriori prediction. This finding corroborates the theory that indirect tax has significant relationship on the real gross domestic product.

B. Statistical Criteria

Real investment showed positive and significant results, with a t-value of 5.692977 and a p-value of 0.000, respectively. Their p-value was less than the 5% level of significance, which explains that Real investment has positive significant effect on real gross domestic product

In Nigeria, the t-value of portfolio investment on productivity is 4.080118 and p-value of 0.003, which was less than the five percent level of significance, respectively, demonstrated this. This finding indicates

that variations in the real gross domestic product is significantly influenced by the size of the real gross domestic product

Based on the outcome, the coefficient of determination R^2 is 0.728706, meaning that the independent variables in the model— Real investment and portfolio investment —explain 72% of the variation in real gross domestic product. Conversely, factors outside of our model account for roughly 73% of the total. This demonstrates even more how well the model fits the data.

The associated probability value of 0.000 indicates that the model's f-statistics value of 158.2535, which measures the combined importance of the explanatory variables, is judged to be statistically significant at the 1 percent level. This suggests that the dependent and independent variables differ significantly from one another.

4.8 Hypotheses Testing

The need to examine the relationship between the actual results data and the stated hypothesis has called for this section. This result will be compared with the statistical criteria to see if the preconceived notion in this research work holds or not. However, if the probability value is less than 0.05%, alternative hypothesis is accepted, but when it is greater than 5% null hypothesis is accepted

Hypothesis One

Ho₁; Real investment has no significant effect on growth of Nigerian economy.

From the result report of our t-test in table 4.3 above, it was observed from the real investment value of 5.692977 with the probability of 0.0000 which is within the desired level of significant (0.05), we therefore reject null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypotheses and conclude that real investment has significant effect on growth of Nigerian economy

Hypothesis Two

Ho₂; Portfolio investment has no significant effect on growth of Nigerian economy

From the forgoing result we find out that computed value for Portfolio investment is 4.080118 while it's probability is 0.003 this show that the Portfolio investment is statistically significant. Based on this analysis we reject (H₀) and accept (H_i), which implies that Portfolio investment has significant effect on growth of Nigerian economy

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Foreign private investment (FPI) has remained a key driver of economic development in both developed and developing countries. In Nigeria, the inflow of foreign capital, technology, and managerial expertise associated with FPI has been recognized as an essential catalyst for industrial growth, employment creation, and overall economic transformation. The study of FPI and economic growth in Nigeria reveals that the country's economic performance has often been influenced by fluctuations in capital inflows, particularly in sectors such as oil and gas, telecommunications, manufacturing, and financial services. Evidence suggests that when properly harnessed, FPI contributes positively to gross domestic product (GDP) growth, enhances technological transfer, improves infrastructural development, and increases Nigeria's integration into the global economy. Foreign investors bring not only financial resources but also advanced skills and global networks that help strengthen the competitiveness of domestic enterprises. Moreover, FPI has the potential to diversify the Nigerian economy, especially in non-oil sectors such as agriculture, renewable energy, real estate, and ICT, thereby reducing the over-dependence on crude oil revenues. The Nigerian government should invest massively in critical infrastructure such as power, roads, railways, and broadband internet to reduce the cost of doing business and make the economy more attractive to foreign investors. Addressing insecurity challenges such as insurgency, banditry, kidnapping, and communal conflicts will be crucial in attracting and retaining long-term investments. Political stability and good governance also provide assurance to investors. Efforts should be made to channel foreign investment into non-oil sectors such as agriculture, manufacturing, ICT, solid minerals, and renewable energy. This will create jobs, enhance industrialization, and promote sustainable growth. Institutions such as the Nigerian Investment Promotion Commission (NIPC) should be further empowered to facilitate and monitor investments.

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